

Effect on Blood Pressure on the Selected Asanas on Untrained Persons

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Abstract

Aim of this study was to find out the effect on Blood Pressure (BP) in the final position of selected asanas. This study was limited to the 16 selected asanas and also to the untrained male of different ages. Total 111 subjects were selected for the study from the different cities. The selected subjects have knowledge of asanas. The pre data was measured in the laying position and post data was measured in the final position of asana. T – test was used to analyze the data. The result of this study indicates that systolic blood pressure and diastolic blood pressure was increased in all asanas except in Tadasana, Parvatasana, Makarasana and Shavasana, in these Asanas blood pressure was decrease or lower than the normal.

Keywords

Systolic Blood Pressure, Untrained person, Diastolic Blood Pressure.

Introduction

All human being have blood and it flow in entire body through the blood vessels with the certain pressure. This pressure is created due to the contraction of heart. The movement of blood in the body is a result of pressure gradient. This means blood flows from a point of high pressure to low pressure. In the systematic circulatory system, the point of highest pressure occurs in the left ventricle during systole, and the difference between this point and the lowest pressure point in the right atrium is the driving force that causes blood to flow throughout the entire systematic circulation.

Blood pressure is the pressure caused by the blood against the wall of the blood vessels. This pressure is created due to the rhythmic activity of heart known as cardiac cycle. In cardiac cycle process heart contract and relax alternately and rhythmically. When heart contract it passes the blood into blood vessels and the pressure in the arteries reach to the peak point which is known as systolic blood pressure. In relax condition of heart the blood in the blood vessels create least pressure which is known as diastolic blood pressure. In normal condition heart works normally and blood pressure will also be normal. But when condition or situation changes and heart comes extra work load this pressure is increase accordingly. When condition or situation changes to normal the heart comes to normal and blood pressure also return to normal condition.

On the basis of previous researches and available literature it is concluded that blood pressure was affected by training and exercise. Beside this blood pressure was also influenced by posture, age, emotion, gender, physical health, and atmosphere. Posture and age is important factors out of these factors.

In present scenario peoples are more conscious for their health. So they do something for their good health some of them prefer exercise, walking and practicing asanas. Asanas are nothing only they are different type of body pattern which is called posture and in yoga it is called as Asanas

In asanas people mold body in different postures and maintain it for some time which is depend on their capacity. According to the available literature there are eighty four lakhs asanas. Asanas are nothing but the pattern of sitting of different species used by them for comfortable sitting. According to the Patanjali "Sthir – Sukham – Asaman" that mean steady and comfort sitting position is known as asanas. All most every asanas might be influenced the blood pressure in different ways. Every asanas creates pressure or changes on human body and it may be varied for every asanas. This pressure/ changes are temporary or permanent. Permanent changes can be visible after long practice but temporary changes can be visible immediately or during the performance. So effect of any activity on human being could be studied from two angles i.e. the immediate effect/ change and long term effect/ change. The immediate effect/ change of any activity was more than the long term effect/ change. In the same way these effects are different in trained and untrained persons. In trained person these changes are very less but in untrained person these changes are high. Due to these points researcher motivates to conduct a study.

Objective of study

To check the immediate effect on blood pressure in the final position of asanas on untrained person this study was conducted and its objective was to (1) compare the post data and pre data mean of each asanas, (2) compare the combine post data means of each asana.

Review of Literature

Pramanik, Sharma, Mishra, Prajapati and Singh evaluate the immediate effect of slow pace bhastrika pranayama for 5 minutes on heart rate and blood pressure and the effect of the same breathing exercise for the same duration of time (5 minutes) following oral intake of hyoscine-N-butylbromide (Buscopan®), a parasympathetic blocker drug. Heart rate and blood pressure of volunteers (n = 39, age = 25–40 years) was recorded. Result indicates that after slow bhastrika pranayamic breathing (respiratory rate 6/min) for 5 minutes, both the systolic and diastolic blood pressure decreased significantly with a slight fall in heart rate. No significant alteration in both blood pressure and heart rate was observed in volunteers who performed the same breathing exercise for the same duration following oral intake of hyoscine-N-butylbromide.

Gunde, Bera and Gore were study to evaluate the effects of some selected yogasanas and similar type of exercises on selected neuro physiological variables like ECG, blood pressure, EEG, SpO₂, respiratory rate, pulse rate. Significant increase in the heart rate, blood pressure, pulse rate and respiratory rate was found when asanas is performed as a exercise.

Jadhav has selected 15 students for the study. But at the end of the study only 10 students remain. Bhujangasana, Sarvangasana, Ardhamathsendrasana, and Halasana, Paschimothanasana were selected for the study. Researcher has given training of above for one month daily 45 minute's course. The age range of participants was 18 to 20 years. After one month training researcher have measured their blood pressure respiration naddichallan before and after asana. Researcher found that in Bhujangasana Sarvangasana and Halasana blood pressure, respiration and naddichallan increases as compared to Paschimothanasana and Ardhamathsendrasana Chakraborty, study to compare the effect of specific exercise, asanas and clinical findings (Resting heart rate, Respiratory rate, Blood pressure, Hemoglobin) of the adults. After experimental programme it was observed that in case of exercise group revealed that resting heart rate, respiratory rate, hemoglobin contain, systolic blood pressure and diastolic blood pressure improved but found insignificant under t –test. In case of asana group resting heart rate, respiratory rate, and hemoglobin contain, insignificantly, but systolic blood pressure and diastolic blood pressure improved significantly.

Divya and Shenbagavalli, study to find out the effects of gymnastics exercise and yoga exercise or asanas on college student. Vital capacity, Heart rate, Breath holding time, systolic blood pressure, and diastolic blood pressure are takes as dependent variable. Researcher found that gymnastic exercise training and yoga practice have significantly vital capacity, breath holding time, heart rate and systolic blood pressure.

Gore studied on the blood pressure (BP) and pulse Rate (PR) before and immediately after 10 rounds of Anulom Vilom pranayama in four different conditions on eight male volunteers who were beginners or fresh students of yoga. Four conditions were: (1) without kumbhaka as well as time ratio; (2) without kumbhaka but with time ratio of 1:2:2; (3) with kumbhaka and time ratio 1:2:2 and (4) with kumbhaka, three bandhas and time ratio of 1:2:2. Results showed that in condition No.1 there was insignificant reduction in BP and increase in PR. In condition No.2 also, an increase in systolic BP by 8.7 mmHg was not significant ($p > 0.05$), where in condition No.3 an increase in SBP by 5.3 mmHg was significant ($p < 0.05$) and in condition No.4 BP increased but not significantly ($p < 0.10$) by 6.8 mmHg. Marginal increase in PR by 3 beats/ min was not significant. The increase in BP due to practice of kumbhaka, bandhas and specific time ratio was found within the

normal range and therefore the traditional technique of Anulom Vilom Pranayama (condition No.3 and 4) are ' physiologically safe' even for the beginners.

Methodology

The present study was delimited to the untrained male candidate of different age and also delimited to the sixteen asanas which are divided into four different groups depends on the position of asanas:

Standing asanas –	Position	Tadasana (AS1),	Trikonasana (AS2),
		Vrikshasana (AS3),	Utkatasana (AS4),
Sitting position asanas –		Padmasana (AS5),	Vajrasana (AS6),
		Parvatasana (AS7),	Paschimothanasana (AS8),
Inverted asanas –	position	Viparitha Karni (AS9),	Sarvangasana (AS10),
		Halasana (AS11),	Shirshasana (AS12),
Laying position asanas –		Shalabhasana (AS13),	Bhujangasana (AS14),
		Makarasana (AS15),	Shavasana (AS16)

On the basis of availability subjects will selected from different places of Uttar Pradesh. Total 111 subjects (One Hundred Eleven) were selected for the subjects of different age group (18 to 65 Years). To check immediate effect of blood pressure on untrained person the selected subjects have knowledge of yoga but they don't practice the asanas. Blood Pressure was tested variable and measured automatically by the instrument, it was measured in mmHg. Pre – data or normal Blood pressure was measured after giving 5 to 10 minutes of rest in shavasana/ supine position. It was taken once in the beginning of the data collection and common for all 16 asanas, whereas as the post data for all 16 asanas was different and collected in 4 days. Data of blood pressure was collected in the final position of every asanas by an instrument. In between the two asanas 2 to 5 minute of rest in supine/ prone position was given to the subjects, so that he comes in normal condition and prepares himself for the next asana.

Statistics Used in the Study

For determining significant difference exist between per data and post data of HR correlated 't' test was used. For determining significant change in gain score of Blood Pressure on different asanas, an analysis of variance (ANOVA) and LSD post hoc test was used to check mean differences. Gain scores for selected variables were calculated by the following method "Post data – Pre data". The +ve value of gain indicates that post data value was higher than the pre data (normal) value and –ve value of gain indicates that post data value was lower than the pre data (normal) value.

Analysis

The data was analyzed and results of the study was presented in the different tables-

Table - 1
't' TEST VALUE OF SYSTOLIC BLOOD PRESSURE

S No	Name of Asana		Normal	Mean	M. Diff	't' – test
1	Tadasana	AS1	121.649	112.189	-9.459	-10.884*
2	Trikonasana	AS2	121.649	129.685	8.036	6.846*
3	Vrikshasana	AS3	121.649	125.315	3.667	4.163*
4	Utkatasana	AS4	121.649	132.964	11.315	12.420*
			121.649	125.038	3.39	
5	Padmasana	AS5	121.649	130.712	9.063	11.223*
6	Vajrasana	AS6	121.649	131.117	9.468	11.689*
7	Parvatasana	AS7	121.649	111.973	-9.676	-10.119*
8	Paschimothanasana	AS8	121.649	133.820	12.171	12.325*
			121.649	126.906	5.257	
9	Viparitha Karni	AS9	121.649	140.730	19.081	14.699*
10	Sarvangasana	AS10	121.649	139.270	17.622	12.831*
11	Halasana	AS11	121.649	146.784	25.135	18.809*
12	Shirshasana	AS12	121.649	147.342	25.694	20.090*
			121.649	143.532	21.883	
13	Shalabhasana	AS13	121.649	133.063	11.414	10.913*
14	Bhujangasana	AS14	121.649	125.432	3.784	4.006*
15	Makarasana	AS15	121.649	117.649	-4.000	-6.987*
16	Shavasana	AS16	121.649	116.595	-5.054	-10.286*
			121.649	123.185	1.536	

* Significant at 0.05 level with df (110) = 1.658

It is clear from the table – 1 that obtained value of 't' for all asanas are higher (irrespective of the ± value) than the tabulated value of 't' (1.658) at 0.05 level, that means there was a significant difference between the pre data of systolic blood pressure and post data of systolic blood pressure. The negative (-ve) value of 't' for asanas AS1, AS7, AS15 and AS16 indicates that systolic blood pressure was lower than the normal and positive (+ve) value of other asanas indicate that systolic blood pressure was higher than the normal.

Fig - 1

Table – 2
ASANA WISE MEAN DIFFERENCE ON GAIN SCORE OF SYSTOLIC BLOOD PRESSURE

1-	AS12		25.694	} 0.559
2-	AS11		25.135	
3-	AS9	} 1.459	19.081	}
4-	AS10		17.622	
5-	AS8		12.171	} 1.667
6-	AS13		11.414	
7-	AS4		11.315	} 2.703
8-	AS6		9.468	
9-	AS5	} 1.432	9.063	} 1.288
10-	AS2		8.036	
11-	AS14		3.784	} 0.117
12-	AS3		3.667	
13-	AS15		-4.000	} 1.054
14-	AS16		-5.054	
15-	AS1		-9.459	} 0.217
16-	AS7		-9.676	

LSD post hoc test value is 2.834

Note :- Bracket indicate that there is no significant difference in the groups.

Table – 2 clearly indicates that gain systolic blood pressure of AS12 had a significantly higher and superior to all other 15 asanas. No significance difference was found (AS12 & AS11), (AS9 & AS10), (AS8, AS13, AS4 & AS6), (AS6, AS5 & AS2), (AS14 & AS3), (AS15 & AS16), (AS1 & AS7). During the inverted asanas systolic blood pressure was increased maximum. In AS15, AS16, AS1 and AS7 gain score of systolic blood pressure have negative value that mean in these asanas systolic blood pressure was lower than the normal.

Table - 3
't' Test Value of Diastolic Blood Pressure

S.No.	Name of Asana		Normal	Mean	M. Diff	't' – test
1	Tadasana	AS1	75.378	68.766	-6.613	-7.640*
2	Trikonasana	AS2	75.378	83.414	8.036	6.770*
3	Vrikshasana	AS3	75.378	77.243	1.865	2.077*
4	Utkatasana	AS4	75.378	87.144	11.766	15.667*
			75.378	79.142	3.764	
5	Padmasana	AS5	75.378	84.423	9.045	11.718*
6	Vajrasana	AS6	75.378	85.261	9.883	13.372*
7	Parvatasana	AS7	75.378	69.144	-6.234	-7.702*
8	Paschimothanasana	AS8	75.378	89.270	13.892	15.398*
			75.378	82.025	6.647	
9	Viparitha Karni	AS9	75.378	90.189	14.811	12.080*
10	Sarvangasana	AS10	75.378	88.153	12.775	8.943*
11	Halasana	AS11	75.378	96.027	20.649	17.972*
12	Shirshasana	AS12	75.378	97.883	22.505	21.608*
			75.378	93.063	17.685	
13	Shalabhasana	AS13	75.378	88.964	13.586	14.341*
14	Bhujangasana	AS14	75.378	84.369	8.991	10.843*
15	Makarasana	AS15	75.378	73.631	-1.748	-2.780*
16	Shavasana	AS16	75.378	72.180	-3.198	-6.065*
			75.378	82.016	6.638	

* Significant at 0.05 level with df (110) = 1.658

It is clear from the table – 3 that obtained value of 't' for all asanas are higher (irrespective of the ± value) than the tabulated value of 't' (1.658) at 0.05 level, that means there was a significant difference between the pre data of diastolic blood pressure and post data of diastolic blood pressure. The negative (-ve) value of 't' for asanas AS1, AS7, AS15 and AS16 indicates that diastolic blood pressure was lower than the normal and positive (+ve) value of other asanas indicate that systolic blood pressure was higher than the normal.

Fig - 2

Table - 4
ASANA WISE MEAN DIFFERENCE ON GAIN SCORE OF DIASTOLIC BLOOD PRESSURE

1-	AS12	22.505	} 1.856
2-	AS11	20.649	
3-	AS9	14.811	} 2.036
4-	AS8	13.892	
5-	AS13	13.586	} 1.883
6-	AS10	12.775	
7-	AS4	11.766	} 1.847
8-	AS6	9.883	
9-	AS5	9.045	} 1.450
10-	AS14	8.991	
11-	AS2	8.036	} 0.379
12-	AS3	1.865	
13-	AS15	-1.748	} 0.379
14-	AS16	-3.198	
15-	AS7	-6.234	} 0.379
16-	AS1	-6.613	
		LSD post hoc test value is 2.675	

Note :- Bracket indicate that there is no significant difference in the groups.

Table - 4 clearly indicates that gain diastolic blood pressure of AS12 and AS13 have same value and have a highest gain of diastolic blood pressure. These two asanas are superior to all other 14 asanas. No significance difference was found between (AS12 & AS11), (AS9, AS8, AS13 & AS10), (AS8, AS13, AS10 & AS4), (AS4 & AS6), (AS6, AS5, AS14 & AS2), (AS15 & AS16) and (AS7 & AS1). During the inverted asanas diastolic blood pressure was increased maximum. In AS15, AS16, AS7 and AS1 gain score of diastolic blood pressure have negative value that mean in these asanas diastolic blood pressure was lower than the normal.

Result and Discussion

In all asana significant difference was found between pre and post data of systolic as well as diastolic blood pressure. AS1, AS7 AS15 and AS16 shows the negative value where as other all asanas shows positive value. Positive value of asanas indicate that blood pressure was increase in these asanas and blood pressure was higher than the normal in the final position of asana whereas negative value indicate that in the final position blood pressure was lower than the normal

Maximum increase in systolic and diastolic blood pressure was noticed in AS12 and AS11. Then higher value of systolic blood pressure was notice in AS9 and AS10 and higher value of diastolic blood pressure was notices in AS9, AS8 and AS10. All these asanas (AS9, AS10, AS11 AS12) come under the category of inverted asanas. So it was concluded from the study that inverted asanas had higher systolic blood pressure than the standing position, lie position and sitting position asanas. In inverted position, blood flow was interrupted and slower down which may result to create high pressure on the blood vessels. According to the available literature blood pressure was also influence by gravity and in these asana blood flow was against the gravity.

Gain score of systolic blood pressure and diastolic blood pressure of AS15 and AS16 was negative or less than the normal. On the basis of available literature systolic blood pressure is decreased in relax position. Both these are relaxed asanas in prone position and supine position respectively, in the both asanas the muscular tension was released, person feels relaxed and blood circulation was normal so these factors may affect the systolic blood pressure.

Gain score of systolic blood pressure and diastolic blood pressure of AS1 and AS7 was also lower than the normal. In the final position of these asanas both hands were above the head. According to the available literature in the book "Text Book of Medical Physiology" and "Review of Medical Physiology" by the author Arthur C Guyton & John E Hall and William F. Ganong respectively due to the effect of gravity systolic blood pressure is decreased as the distance above the heart level is increased.

Conclusion

In the final position of different asanas except AS1, AS7, AS15 and AS16 blood pressure was increased. AS12 is considered as the most difficult asanas because blood pressure was increased maximum. The present study had found that some of the asanas which can give high increase in the blood pressure. As asanas are perform by many peoples and in all age groups. It is suggested that people who are having cardiac problem and irregular blood pressure problem must aware about those asanas, which can give a high increase in their blood pressure. They should also use expert guidance and must consult their doctor before performing any difficult asanas.

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